

PSEUDOSOLITONS ON THE GENERALIZED CONFORMABLE KORTEWEG-DE VRIES EQUATION

J. NOYOLA-RODRÍGUEZ, J.C. HERNANDEZ GÓMEZ, S. GATICA RAMOS
AND JAIR J. PINEDA-PINEDA

ABSTRACT. We consider the Korteweg-de Vries (KdV) model with classical derivative for outflows on water surfaces where the medium is assumed to be shallow and replace the classical first order derivative in time by the generalized conformable fractional derivative of order α with $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ and different kernels $T(t, \alpha)$ defining fractional derivative mentioned above. We prove the existence of new soliton-like traveling waves which we call *pseudodolitons* propagating in a not necessarily linear wavefront. We study the dynamical system associated to the equation with generalized conformable fractional derivative and calculate some balance laws for the energy. In general it is concluded that the pseudosolitons have two main characteristics depending on the kernel of the fractional derivative. If the fractional derivative is conformable then the pseudosolitons propagate over large distances preserving their shape and amplitude and converge to the soliton-like solutions of the classical KdV when $\alpha \rightarrow 1$. On the other hand, if the derivative is nonconformable then the pseudosolitons only preserve the properties of the soliton-like traveling waves.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fractional calculus is as old as classical calculus since both originated thanks to the work of Newton and Leibniz in the 17th century. However, it is well known that fractional calculus generalizes the concept of derivative and integration to all orders not necessarily integers (see [9, 11, 16]). Nowadays, some non-local fractional operators (*e.g.*, Caputo and Riemann-Liouville) have been used to describe natural phenomena that evolve in time considering what happened within a time interval behind the studied process, (see [4, 12, 19]).

A few years later, a new definition of local fractional derivative is introduced, which extends the definition of the limit of the classical derivative. This type of derivative is known as a conformable derivative if the angle of the tangent line to the curve is preserved, otherwise it is said to be a non-conformable derivative, (see [1, 3, 5, 6, 10]). In [3] a logistic growth model is analyzed using the generalized conformable derivative with kernel $T(t, \alpha) = e^{(\alpha-1)t}$ and $\alpha = 0.85$, where it is observed that with less real data a good approximation is obtained that using the classical derivative with more real data. On the other hand, in [12–14, 19] the KdV equation is analyzed using the fractional derivatives of Caputo and Riemann-Liouville type. In [14] the method of fictitious integration and group preservation is used to convert

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the KdV equation with Caputo-type fractional derivative into a system of equations which is solved numerically. In [13] the Caputo-type KdV equation is solved numerically using the variational iteration method. In general, in the literature on the fractional KdV equation only numerical solutions are presented.

In this paper we consider the generalized conformable fractional derivative [6] in order to study the classical KdV equation. We introduce the fractional derivative in the time variable in the form:

$$G_T^\alpha u(x, t) + \frac{\partial u(x, t)^2}{\partial x} + \varepsilon \frac{\partial^3 u(x, t)}{\partial x^3} = 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad t > 0. \tag{1.1}$$

Here G_T^α denotes the fractional derivative with respect to the time variable, $T \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} T(t, \alpha)$ is a function that depends on t , and $\alpha \in \mathbb{Q}$ is a constant that determines the order of generalized conformable fractional derivative, $u \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} u(x, t)$ represents the volume of the water surface with respect to the equilibrium state $u(x, t) = 0$ and ε a positive constant measuring the level of linear dispersion. In the case of $\alpha = 1$ the equation (1.1) is the well known classical KdV equation with ordinary derivative. The classical KdV equation has been well-studied since the year 1960, when solitons were discovered and the Inverse Scattering Transform method was created, (see [2, 8, 21] and their references therein), where it was proved that this equation is integrable and admits solitons. Studies have also been carried out on a generalization of the nonlinear term of (1.1) with $\alpha = 1$ in the form: u^m such equations are known as GKdV, and important results are obtained, among them, is obtained for $m = 2$ and $m = 3$, are the only cases in which the equation is integrable, the solutions are also stable. For $m = 4$ the solutions are stable, for $m = 5$ the solutions are conditionally stable and to $m \geq 6$ the solutions are unstable, (see [7, 8, 15, 17, 18], and its references therein). In more recent years, the behavior of traveling waves for KdV has been studied using Caputo and Riemann-Liouville type fractional derivatives (see [12–14, 19]).

Non-local fractional operators such as the Riemann-Liouville and Caputo derivatives have the property of storing memory of a study process. At the same time, this property makes it very difficult to find exact solutions to non-linear problems, (see [12, 14]). Our interest in studying the conformable KdV equation (1.1) arises with the appearance of local fractional operators (*e.g.*, the conformable and nonconformable fractional derivative). In (1.1) if the kernel T is such that if $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ then the equation (1.1) tends to the classical KdV it is conformable operator otherwise it is nonconformable. In order to solve problem (1.1) we used the techniques defined in [15, 18], *i.e.* we propose a smooth function $\omega(\eta)$, with $\eta = (x - ct)$ and $\omega(\eta) \rightarrow 0$ when $\eta \rightarrow \pm\infty$. For the case of the generalized conformable fractional derivative we generalize the wavefront with a function $\varphi(t)$ that depends on the kernel of the fractional derivative and present new solutions which we call pseudosolitons. These new solutions have the following properties based on the kernel T of the generalized conformable derivative in consideration: If conformable G_T^α derivative and the pseudosolitons have the same behavior as the solitons except for a slides at the initial point of the wave when α is sufficiently small, converge to the solitons of the classical KdV when α tends to 1 and satisfy the soliton interaction phenomenon, (see [7, 17, 21]). If we consider G_T^α nonconformable then pseudosolitons do not converge to classical solitons but propagate similarly to solitons on an exponential wavefront and also satisfy the soliton interaction process. In addition, we analyze the dynamical system of (1.1) and find homoclinic orbits associated to pseudosolitons also it is observed that when $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ the homoclinic orbits disappear and when $\alpha < 0$ the equilibrium points invert their properties. The analysis is divided into two

cases depending on the wave velocity parameter. Phase portrait, numerical simulations and mass and energy balance laws confirm the analytical description of pseudosoliton.

2. SOLITONS AND PSEUDOSOLITONS

In the first place, let us recall some important definitions given in [15, 18] to define the soliton-type traveling waves associated with the classical derivative. We will also determine the generalized conformable fractional derivative as in [3, 6] and consequently explain the type of waves we are going to study related to the fractional derivative.

Definition 2.1 (The following definition appears in [15, 18]). A function

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, t) &= A\omega(\eta), \\ \eta &= \beta(x - Vt - x_0)/\varepsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

is a soliton-type traveling wave if

$$\beta = \beta(A), \quad V = V(A),$$

A a free parameter that measures the amplitude of the wave, $\omega(\eta) \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^1)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^k}{d\eta^k} \omega(\eta) &\rightarrow 0, \quad \text{if } \eta \rightarrow \pm\infty, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \\ \omega(0) &= 1. \end{aligned}$$

Traveling waves (2.1) have the property known as “collision of solitons” this phenomenon occurs when two or more solitons merge around a point and then separate, returning to their original shape and velocity except for a shift in the respective wave fronts, (see [7, 17] and their references therein). In this work, it is observed that pseudosolitons satisfy the aforementioned phenomenon.

Regarding the generalized conformable fractional derivative, we have the following definition that appears in [3, 6].

Definition 2.2. Given an interval $I \subset \mathbb{R}$, $f: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and a positive continuous function $T(t, \alpha)$ on I the derivative $G_T^\alpha f$ of f of order α at the point $t \in I$ is defined by

$$G_T^\alpha f(t) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{h^{\lceil \alpha \rceil}} \sum_{k=0}^{\lceil \alpha \rceil} (-1)^k \binom{\lceil \alpha \rceil}{k} f(t - khT(t, \alpha)), \quad (2.2)$$

where $\lceil \alpha \rceil$ denotes the upper integer part of α . To calculate the fractional derivatives at the extreme values of the interval, the limit of the function is calculated to the right and to the left of zero respectively.

If the limit of the right hand side (2.2) exists then we say that the function f is G_T^α -differentiable. Moreover, the fractional derivative satisfies all the properties of the classical derivative, particularly, if $T(t, \alpha) = t^{\lceil \alpha \rceil - \alpha}$ we obtain the n -th classical derivative of integer order for the function f .

We will now define the type of traveling waves to be considered, which conserve some properties of solitons (2.1).

Definition 2.3. A function

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, t) &= A\omega(\eta, \alpha), \\ \eta &= \beta(x - V\varphi(t) - x_0)/\varepsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

is a pseudosoliton-type solution if

$$\beta = \beta(A), \quad V = V(A), \quad \varphi(t) = \varphi(t, A, \alpha),$$

A is a free parameter that measures the amplitude of the wave, α a positive parameter, $\omega(\eta, \alpha) \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^1)$ and

$$\frac{d^k}{d\eta^k} \omega(\eta, \alpha) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{if } \eta \rightarrow \pm\infty, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \tag{2.4}$$

$$\omega(0, \alpha) = 1 \quad \text{or} \quad \omega(0, \alpha) = \alpha \tag{2.5}$$

uniformly in α .

The α parameter measures the level of diffusion of the system and we say that we have sub-diffusion if $\alpha < 1$ and super-diffusion if $\alpha > 1$.

The first result is the existence of pseudosolitons for the conformable KdV equation:

Theorem 2.1. *Let $T(t, \alpha)$ be the kernel of the fractional derivative (2.2), $1/T(t, \alpha) \in L^1_{loc}(\Omega)$, $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^+$. By defining*

$$\varphi(t) = c(\alpha) \int_0^t \frac{dz}{T(z, \alpha)} + T(0, \alpha). \tag{2.6}$$

Here $c(\alpha)$ is a constant that depends on α and rescaling $\beta = \sqrt{(2/3)A}$. Then equation (1.1) admits the pseudosolitons-like solutions (2.4)

$$u(x, t) = A \operatorname{sech}^2 \left(\frac{\beta(x - V\varphi(t) - x_0)}{2\varepsilon} \right), \quad \text{if } V = (2/3)A\alpha^{-1} \tag{2.7}$$

and

$$u(x, t) = \alpha A \operatorname{sech}^2 \left(\frac{\beta\sqrt{\alpha}(x - V\varphi(t) - x_0)}{2\varepsilon} \right), \quad \text{if } V = (2/3)A, \tag{2.8}$$

where V is the velocity of the wave and A is the amplitude of the pseudosoliton.

Proof. We write *anzats* in the form (2.3) with $\varphi(t)$ defined in (2.6) here V is the velocity of the pseudosoliton. Considering the properties (2.4) and (2.5), we calculate the derivatives and substitute in (1.1) obtaining the inverse problem:

$$-\alpha V \omega + A \omega^2 + (2/3)A \frac{d^2\omega}{d\eta^2} = 0. \tag{2.9}$$

Using again the properties (2.4) and assuming that ω satisfies the property (2.5) the problem (2.9) transforms to a first order differential equation:

$$\frac{d\omega}{d\eta} = -\omega \sqrt{\frac{3\alpha V}{2A} - \omega}, \quad \eta > 0. \tag{2.10}$$

To obtain the solution in the complete domain $(-\infty, \infty)$ we use the still unknown parameter V that allow us to obtain ω as an even function. If $V = (2/3)A\alpha^{-1}$ then of (2.10) we obtain that ω satisfies the first property given in (2.5) if and only if ω is an even function. We find the explicit solution of (2.10) solving the following problem:

$$\eta = \int_\omega^1 \frac{dz}{z\sqrt{1-z}}.$$

Getting the solution (2.7) to the problem (1.1).

If the wave velocity does not depend on the order of the fractional derivative as follows $V = (2/3)A$ then ω is an even function if and only if satisfies the second property in (2.5). Therefore, in order to find this solution we go from (2.10) to solve the following problem:

$$\eta = \int_{\omega}^{\alpha} \frac{dz}{z\sqrt{\alpha-z}}.$$

Obtaining the solution to the problem (1.1) given in (2.8). □

Note that if the derivative G_T^{α} in (2.2) is conformable then when $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ one has that $\varphi(t, \alpha) \rightarrow t$ and the solutions (2.7) and (2.8) converge to the soliton-like solution given in [7], with $m = 2$. If the derivative G_T^{α} is nonconformable then $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1} \varphi(t, \alpha) \neq t$ and the traveling waves (2.7) and (2.8) unlike the solitons propagate on a nonlinear wavefront.

3. DYNAMIC SYSTEM OF PSEUDOSOLITONS

Now let us study the phase portrait of pseudosolitons for the conformable KdV equation (1.1) from the point of view of dynamical system.

We start from the inverse problem (2.9) and we pass to the nonlinear system:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{d\eta} &= F(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}), \\ \frac{d\mathbf{y}}{d\eta} &= G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}), \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

where $\mathbf{x} = \omega$, $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x}'$, $F(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{y}$ and $G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = (3/2)\mathbf{x}\{(\alpha V)/A - \mathbf{x}\}$. Here $\mathbf{x} \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} \mathbf{x}(\eta, \alpha)$ and $\mathbf{y} \stackrel{\text{def.}}{=} \mathbf{y}(\eta, \alpha)$. System (3.1) has two equilibrium points; $\mathbf{x}_1 = (0, 0)$ and $\mathbf{y}_1 = ((\alpha V)/A, 0)$. For the analysis of the equilibrium points we divide the work into two parts depending on the velocity parameter V .

3.1. Case I. We study the dynamical system of the (3.1) when V does not depend on the order of the fractional derivative.

Lemma 3.1. *Let the velocity $V = (2/3)A$. Then there exists a homoclinic orbit Γ_0 in the system (3.1) associated with the solution (2.8). Moreover the parameter α is a transcritical bifurcation parameter of the system (3.1).*

Proof. If $V = (2/3)A$ then the equilibrium points of the system (3.1) are written in the form $\mathbf{x}_1 = (0, 0)$ and $\mathbf{y}_1 = ((2/3)\alpha, 0)$.

Considering the flow function

$$\varphi_1(\eta, \mathbf{c}) = (c_1 \operatorname{sech}^2(\eta/2), -c_2 \operatorname{sech}^2(\eta/2) \tanh(\eta/2)), \tag{3.2}$$

with $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, c_2)$.

Let $\mathbf{c}_1 = \varphi_1(0) = (1, 0)$ then $\varphi_1(\eta, \mathbf{c}_1)$ represents the unique trajectory such that $\lim_{\eta \rightarrow \pm\infty} \varphi_1(\eta, \mathbf{c}_1) = \mathbf{x}_1$. Therefore $\Gamma_0 = \varphi_1(\eta, \mathbf{c}_1)$ is a homoclinic orbit of the system (3.1). The next step is to analyze the equilibrium points separately. For the equilibrium point \mathbf{x}_1 the Jacobian matrix has the eigenvalues $\lambda_1 = -\sqrt{\alpha}$ and $\lambda_2 = \sqrt{\alpha}$, if $\alpha > 0$ then it is a saddle point, if $\alpha = 0$ it is a degenerate point and if $\alpha < 0$ then \mathbf{x}_1 is a center. For the point \mathbf{y}_1 the Jacobian matrix has eigenvalues the following eigenvalues $\lambda_1 = i\sqrt{\alpha}$ and $\lambda_2 = -i\sqrt{\alpha}$ therefore if $\alpha > 0$ then \mathbf{y}_1 is a center, if $\alpha = 0$ it is a degenerate point and if $\alpha < 0$ then \mathbf{y}_1 is a saddle point. This shows that the parameter α implies a transcritical

bifurcation in the system (3.1) so that the equilibrium points exchange their positions in the phase portrait of the system (3.1); see Fig. 1. Moreover it is clear that when $\alpha = 0$ the separatrix vanishes. □

FIGURE 1. Transcritical bifurcation with respect to the parameter α . In 1A shows that if $\alpha < 0$ then the equilibrium point $\mathbf{x}_1 = (0, 0)$ is shown as a center and the equilibrium point $\mathbf{y}_1 = (2\alpha/3, 0)$ as a saddle point. In 1B if $\alpha = 0$ then the homoclinic orbit disappears and consequently we have only a degenerate $\mathbf{x}_1 = \mathbf{y}_1 = (0, 0)$ equilibrium point. Finally, the subfigure 1C proves that if $\alpha > 0$ then the equilibrium point $\mathbf{x}_1 = (0, 0)$ is a saddle point and $\mathbf{y}_1 = (2\alpha/3, 0)$ is a center point.

3.2. Case II. If we consider the case when the wave velocity depends on the parameter α in the form $V = (2/3)\alpha^{-1}A$ then the system (3.1) has only two equilibrium points; $\mathbf{x}_1 = (0, 0)$ and $\mathbf{y}_1 = (2/3, 0)$. Consequently linearizing the system (3.1) with the Jacobian matrix we obtain that \mathbf{x}_1 is a saddle point and \mathbf{y}_1 is a center. Similar to case I there also exists a homoclinic orbit generated by the following curve:

$$\varphi_2(\eta, \mathbf{c}_2) = (\alpha \operatorname{sech}^2(\sqrt{\alpha}\eta/2), 0), \tag{3.3}$$

with $\mathbf{c}_2 = (\alpha, 0)$. In this case, we find that the equilibrium points of system (3.1) are independent of the parameter α . Therefore if $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ then no homoclinic orbit exists since $\varphi_2(\eta, \mathbf{c}_2) = 0$. If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ then there is a homoclinic orbit generated by the curve $\varphi_2(\eta, \mathbf{c}_0)$ defined in (3.3) associated with the pseudosolitons (2.7), as shown in the Fig.2. For this situation the homoclinic orbit of the system (3.1) coincides with the homoclinic orbit of the KdV with ordinary derivative. Thus, the following Lemma 3.2 is demonstrated:

Lemma 3.2. *Let the velocity $V = (2/3)A\alpha^{-1}$. Then there is a homoclinic orbit of the system (3.1) associated to the solution (2.7).*

Proposition 3.1. *System (3.1) is a Hamiltonian system.*

Proof. By defining the real value function

$$H(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{\mathbf{y}^2}{2} + \frac{\mathbf{x}^3}{2} - \frac{3\alpha V}{4A}\mathbf{x}^2,$$

over the open $U \in \mathbb{R}^2$ then it is clear that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{d\eta} &= \frac{\partial H}{\partial \mathbf{y}}, \\ \frac{d\mathbf{y}}{d\eta} &= -\frac{\partial H}{\partial \mathbf{x}}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the system (3.1) is a Hamiltonian function.

Lemmas 3.1 and 3.2 prove the property of the Hamiltonian system (3.1), that is the system is conservative and its equilibrium points are saddle points or centers. \square

FIGURE 2. Phase portrait of the system (3.1), with velocity $V = (2/3)A\alpha^{-1}$. Here it is shown that $\mathbf{x}_1 = (0,0)$ is a saddle point and $\mathbf{y}_1 = (2/3,0)$ is a center. In addition shown is the homoclinic orbit leaving \mathbf{x}_1 it passes through point \mathbf{c}_2 and returns to the same equilibrium point.

4. BALANCE LAWS AND SIMULATIONS

Proposition 3.1 guarantees that the system (3.1) is conservative so that the conformable KdV equation (1.1) satisfies the following balance laws

$$T(t, \alpha) \frac{d}{dt} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u \, dx = 0, \tag{4.1}$$

$$T(t, \alpha) \frac{d}{dt} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 \, dx = 0. \tag{4.2}$$

The energy balance law (4.1) and the mass balance law (4.2) are obtained by multiplying (1.1) by 1 and u and integrating respectively. Note that both conservation laws are weighted

by the value $T(t, \alpha)$, this implies that the way laws (4.1) and (4.2) are satisfied depends on the kernel of the fractional derivative. For some functions $T(t, \alpha)$ we can observe a jump at the beginning of the wave, *i.e.*, for small values of t and α the wavefront grows very fast and then stabilizes, see Fig. 5 and Fig. 7.

FIGURE 3. Behavior of the wavefront $x - V\varphi(t)$, with respect to the parameter α , $V = (2/3)A\alpha^{-1}$ and $\varphi(t)$ defined in (2.6) with kernel $T(t, \alpha) = t^{1-\alpha}$.

4.1. Example 1. We consider the equation (1.1) with different values of $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $V = (2/3)A\alpha^{-1}$. In this case there is a shift in the propagation of the pseudosoliton when α is sufficiently small, see Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 below.

FIGURE 4. Propagation of different pseudosolitons with speed $V = (2/3)A\alpha^{-1}$, $A = 1.5$ and $t = 2$. Subfigure 4A shows the propagation of a pseudosoliton with $\alpha = 1$ which is exactly the soliton of the classical KdV. In subfigure 4B shows the propagation of a pseudosoliton with $\alpha = 3/4$ of the conformable KdV.

FIGURE 5. Propagation of different pseudosolitons of the conformable KdV equation with speed $V = (2/3)A\alpha^{-1}$, $A = 1.5$ and $t = 2$. Subfigure 5A shows the propagation of a pseudosoliton with $\alpha = 1/2$ and subfigure 5B shows the propagation of a pseudosoliton with $\alpha = 1/4$. Both figures show the shift of the wave propagation.

4.2. **Example 2.** Now we consider the conformable KdV equation (1.1) with different values of $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $V = (2/3)A$. In this case there is also a shift in the propagation of the pseudosoliton at the same time the amplitude of the wave disappears when α is sufficiently small, see Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 below.

FIGURE 6. Propagation of different pseudosolitons with velocity that does not depend on the order of the fractional derivative with $A = 1.5$ and $t = 2$. In Subfigure 6A show the soliton of the classical KdV and subfigure 6B shows a very small shift in the propagation and the amplitude decreases to a value of $A = 1.125$.

FIGURE 7. Propagation of different pseudosolitons with $V = (2/3)A$ and $t = 2$. Subfigure 7A and subfigure 7B show the phenomenon of shifts in the propagation of waves with amplitudes reduced to 0.75 and 0.375, respectively.

4.3. Example 3. In this example we consider the non-conformable KdV equation (1.1) (*i.e.* we use the fractional derivative with kernel $T(t, \alpha) = e^{-\alpha t}$, it is clear that the tangency angle is not preserved when $\alpha \rightarrow 1$.) We do some simulations for different values $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and we observe that the pseudosolitons are strongly stable for all values of parameter α and exponential wavefront, see Fig. 8.

FIGURE 8. Propagation of different pseudosolitons with $V = (2/3)A$, $A = 1.5$ and $t = 2.5$. Subfigure 8A shows the propagation of a pseudosoliton of the non-conformable differential equation of integer order $\alpha = 1$ and subfigure 8B shows the propagation of a pseudosoliton of the non-conformable fractional differential equation of order $\alpha = 1/4$.

In the case of Example 3 for pseudosolitons traveling with a velocity that does depend on the order of the fractional derivative, the waves propagate in the same way as seen Figure 8 but with smaller amplitude and a motion at the initial position.

Remark 4.1. The pseudosoliton-type traveling waves obtained using the generalized conformable and nonconformable derivative have the same behavior as the soliton-type traveling waves. Moreover, they satisfy the soliton interaction process. Fig. 9 shows the collision of a

conformable pseudosoliton and a nonconformable pseudosoliton both with the same amplitude and time interval $t = 3.5$, see Fig. 9.

FIGURE 9. Collision of two pseudosolitons with the same amplitude; the first pseudosoliton positioned at $x_{10} = 0.4$ is obtained with a non conformable derivative and kernel $T(t, \alpha) = e^{-\alpha t}$ and the second pseudosoliton positioned at $x_{20} = 3$ is obtained with conformable derivative and kernel $T(t, \alpha) = t^{-\alpha}$. Both solitons have amplitude 1.5.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have proved the existence of soliton-type traveling waves for the KdV equation with generalized conformable fractional derivative, which we call pseudosolitons. These traveling waves like solitons, propagate over large distances while conserving their shape, velocity and amplitude. However, these new solutions have the following characteristics depending on the order of the conformable fractional derivative and its kernel:

- (1) If the kernel of the fractional derivative is conformable it is observed that the pseudosolitons propagate on a nonlinear wavefront and if $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ the waves disappear and if $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ then the pseudosoliton-like traveling waves converge to the solitons of the classical KdV. In particular, if $T(t, \alpha) = t^{1-\alpha}$ in (2.2) then one has that the solutions (2.7)-(2.8) tend to the solution of the KdV classical. On the other hand if $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ then they vanish in two ways. The first one the amplitude tend to zero in (2.8) and see Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. In the second form it is observed that the pseudosoliton velocity tends to infinity, see Fig. 3, Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.
- (2) If the kernel of the fractional derivative is not conformable it is observed that the pseudosolitons propagate on a nonlinear wavefront, if $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ or $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ the pseudosolitons propagate over long distances while retaining their shape, velocity and amplitude. In particular if $T(t, \alpha) = e^{-\alpha t}$ in (2.2) waves propagate over an exponential wave front, see Fig. 8.

Another important feature of pseudosoliton-type traveling waves is that they satisfy the pseudosoliton interaction process and even for waves having the same amplitude. Note that classical KdV solitons do not satisfy the interaction process if they have the same amplitude.

As future work we intend to study the KdV equation with generalized conformable fractional derivative in the nonlinear term and in the dispersive term using numerical methods.

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Universidad Autónoma de Guerrero
Facultad de Matemáticas. Ext. Acapulco
Carlos E. Adame 54, 39650 Acapulco de Juárez, Guerrero, México
E-mail address: 20264@uagro.mx

Universidad Autónoma de Guerrero
Facultad de Matemáticas. Ext. Acapulco
Carlos E. Adame 54, 39650 Acapulco de Juárez, Guerrero, México
E-mail address: jcarloshg@gmail.com

Universidad Autónoma de Guerrero
Facultad de Matemáticas. Ext. Acapulco
Carlos E. Adame 54, 39650 Acapulco de Juárez, Guerrero, México
E-mail address: 13342327@uagro.mx

Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla
Instituto de Ciencias (IC)
Ecology and Survival of Microorganisms Research Group
Laboratorio de Ecología Molecular Microbiana
Puebla 72570, México

§

Universidad Autónoma de Guerrero
Facultad de Matemáticas. Ext. Iguala
Carretera Federal Iguala-Taxco, Iguala de la Independencia 40000, México
E-mail address: jpineda@uagro.mx